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Table of contents

Executive Summary	1
List of abbreviations, acronyms and definitions	2
List of figures	3
List of tables	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Project quality assurance plan	5
2.1 Key roles for quality assurance.....	5
2.2 Quality of the project deliverables.....	6
2.3 Deliverable writing.....	7
2.3.1 Templates for deliverables, presentations and meetings.....	8
2.4 Quality of communication between the partners-meetings.....	8
3 Risks management strategy	9
3.1 Risk identification.....	10
3.2 Risk assessment.....	10
3.3 Risk treatment action plan.....	12
3.4 Risk monitoring and report.....	12
Conclusions	17
References	18

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Executive Summary

This document deliverable D1.2 “Risk management and project quality plan” presents a strategy to ensure excellent performance within SPATRA by means of quality assurance and timely risk detection and mitigate potential technical and scientific risks. The document presents a set of adopted procedures to ensure the general quality of the project actions such as communication within and between the work packages (WP), effective meetings, high quality of the deliverable documents and publications. The potential risks, which could prevent successful implementation of the project milestones, are summarized and classified according to their potential effect on the project. High quality of project internal communication ensures constant risk monitoring and reporting. Already at this point mitigation strategies for potential major risks are suggested. In this way, it is ensured that the requirements and conditions of the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium agreement (CA) and Description of Action (DoA) are fully applicable.

The following document provide additional perspectives for the present work:

- D1.1 Project management plan.

List of abbreviations, acronyms and definitions

Abbreviation / Acronym	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
PC	Project Coordinator
R&D	Research and Development
SPATRA	Space-Based Applications For Transport Monitoring And Management
VIIRS	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite
WP	Work Package
DE	Deliverable Editors
DC	Deliverable Contributors
WPL	Work Package Leder
DR	Deliverable Reviewers
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System

List of figures

Figure 1. Methodology of risk management within SPATRA.	10
Figure 2. Risks matrix (self-created).	12

List of tables

Table 1. Internal reviewers of SPATRA deliverables	7
Table 2. Five levels of risk classifications for risk assessment	11
Table 3. Five levels of risk probability	11
Table 4. Critical risks and risk management strategy	14

1 Introduction

This document outlines the Quality Assurance procedures to be adopted within SPATRA, focusing on the deliverable planning, writing, and reviewing processes. Its aim is to ensure the excellence of all project outputs directed towards the European Commission and other external entities. The primary purpose of D1.2 is to serve as a guiding document for the partners of the SPATRA project, aiding various contributors and internal stakeholders across all SPATRA deliverables. D1.2 strives to offer essential guidelines that ensure high-quality, standardized, and succinct deliverables, thereby enhancing the clarity of the project's results by: i) defining the roles and responsibilities of all partners involved in the creation, review, and delivery of a deliverable, ii) outlining a clear and effective Quality Assurance process to be adhered to throughout the project's duration, iii) facilitating a smooth workflow among planning, writing, and reviewing stages of a deliverable, and iv) providing a unified set of protocols for the dissemination of project outcomes.

Together with D1.1 “Project management plan”, which offers general management guidelines, these documents present a comprehensive view of the overall SPATRA quality assurance and internal management processes. This approach ensures a high level of collaboration among partners, leading to positive project results.

Produced within the WP1 “Project Management” work package, this document is intended for project partners and Commission services. It lays out internal procedures and advice to secure the production of high-quality deliverables. Management teams (Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, WP leaders) can utilize this document to monitor the progress of all deliverables, track responsible partners, deadlines, and interim statuses, and to take proactive steps (as outlined in the Project management plan – D1.1) if a deliverable's progress does not match its planned trajectory. Furthermore, Deliverable Editors (DE) may find this document useful as a reminder of the necessary steps for adequate resource planning and responsibility allocation among Deliverable Contributors (DC). It also serves as a guideline for proper deliverable formatting, a source for templates, and as a reminder of the protocols surrounding the multi-contributor process within SPATRA.

The document has the following structure:

- **Project quality assurance plan** of this document presents quality assurance plan within SPATRA, focussing on key roles and responsibilities of the partners to ensure smooth communication within the project and high quality the project deliverables.
- **Risks management strategy** of this document contains SPATRA risk management strategy. Novel R&D may be prone to risks which need to be identified and responded to in due time. In SPATRA, constant risks monitoring, and their evaluation is planned, and a response plan is laid out.

2 Project quality assurance plan

As an essential part of the SPATRA project management, the Project Quality Plan should provide the solid ground for successful, timely and quality implementation of the project activities. It forms a common standard to be applied and followed throughout the project lifetime. For that purpose, it defines the set of procedures to be followed in order to secure that:

- ✓ the requirements and conditions of Grant Agreement (GA) are fully applied and followed by all partners,
- ✓ all requirements for communication and reporting are fulfilled,
- ✓ all partners' rights and obligations defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA) are fulfilled,
- ✓ all project activities are realized in accordance with the plan outlined in the Description of Action (DoA).

2.1 Key roles for quality assurance

The following key roles and respective responsibilities are defined within the context of Quality Assurance in order to accomplish the goals as mentioned in the above sections.

- ✓ **Project Coordinator and Technical Manager:** The Project Coordinator and Technical Manager carry the overall responsibility for the correct application of the Quality Assurance processes by all relevant stakeholders, the timely delivery of all deliverables or the early recognition of deviations and the triggering of appropriate actions and finally assuring the quality of all SPATRA deliverables. The Project Coordinator and Technical Manager will perform a check on the deliverable 14 days prior to the deadline while the Project Coordinator will receive the deliverable 2 days prior to the deadline and provide the final approval for the submission of each deliverable to the EC. The Project Coordinator is also tasked with uploading the final version of each deliverable to the EC portal.
- ✓ **Deliverable Editor (DE):** The deliverable editor carries the responsibility for delivering a well-written, concise, and complete document in a timely fashion. The Deliverable Editor is responsible for making a realistic plan for the deliverable writing phase, for assigning the responsibility of different sections to different contributors, for organizing the teamwork and for facilitating the different Deliverable Contributors to perform their tasks in the best way possible. The creation of a Table of Contents (ToC) and a timetable for the work-plan also falls within the responsibilities of the Deliverable Editor which is also the main contact point for the specific deliverable. The Deliverable Editor is also responsible for the direct monitoring of the writing process and is obliged to raise an alarm towards higher management (Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, WP leader) in cases where significant delays are observed, or the process is hindered by specific difficulties, in order to trigger appropriate management or mitigation actions. Finally, the Deliverable Editor also performs the content consolidation from the different Deliverable Contributors, the final editing and formatting of the document and is responsible for releasing the first full draft to the reviewers at least 2 weeks prior to the deadline of the deliverable.

- ✓ Deliverable Contributors (DC): The deliverable contributors are defined as the participants of the respective Task that contribute to the deliverable in any fashion (providing content, creating figures and Tables, etc.). The Deliverable Contributors have to provide all relevant content depicting the outcome of the relevant SPATRA activities under the guidance of the Deliverable Editor and according to the work split agreed during the planning phase of the deliverable. Participation in team calls, direct feedback to other contributors, text writing and editing are part of the Deliverable Contributors immediate responsibilities, at the discretion of the Task Leaders
- ✓ Task Leaders (TL) manage the engagement of the DC during the reporting phase, assigning the DC roles within their respective task and overseeing the overall task progress regarding a given Deliverable, ensuring timely availability of the task-related content to the DE.
- ✓ Deliverable Reviewers (DR): The deliverable reviewers range between one and two and have been assigned to each deliverable from the start of the project. The DRs have the responsibility to perform a detailed and concise review according to the guidelines presented in this document (Section 2.2) aiming to ensure the conformity of the deliverable to the high-quality standards of SPATRA.
- ✓ Work Package Leader (WPL): The Work Package Leader participates also in the review process of the deliverables within the respective work package.

2.2 Quality of the project deliverables

It is recognised that the SPATRA project requires procedures for ensuring the sustained high quality of its results to be in place, particularly since the results are being generated in a collaborative manner with Deliverable Contributors. High quality results are a key factor to ensure the success of the project, particularly in relation to the acceptance of the results by relevant stakeholders. SPATRA has adopted a peer-review process for ensuring sustained quality of its results:

- ✓ All deliverables have been assigned to an internal reviewer representing different partners, who are not (directly) involved in the drafting of the respective deliverable. Their task is to ensure that the overall technical quality and presentation reflects a high standard. In the case where the person designated as a reviewer has been involved in the preparation of the deliverable, an alternative independent reviewer should be agreed by the person responsible for the deliverable and the reviewer.
- ✓ Each deliverable has a due date, which is stated in the list of deliverables in DoA (and GA - PartA). The internal deadline for each deliverable draft is set before the external due date. Partners responsible for the deliverable are to communicate directly with the assigned internal reviewers whilst including the Project Coordinator in the dialogue.
- ✓ The document is sent to its internal reviewer who will review the document. This procedure ensures that enough time is available to address reviewers' comments and allow for high quality deliverables.

- ✓ The content must reflect the state-of-the-art research. Internal reviewers should also ensure that the use of language is correct, and the document is free of typographical errors and the formatting is proper and consistent throughout the document.

The list of deliverable (internal) reviewers as agreed by the project consortium for the SPATRA deliverables is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Deliverable (internal) reviewers of SPATRA deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	WP No.	Short Name of Lead Participant	Delivery Date (in months)	Internal Reviewers
D1.1	Project Management Plan (PMP)	1	OHB-DS	M2	ZENRS, UNI
D1.2	Risk management and project quality plan	1	OHB-DS	M3	ZENE
D1.3	Data Management Plan	1	OHB-DS	M5	ZENRS, UNI
D2.1	Requirements and use cases specifications	2	UNI	M6	Nelt, OHB-DS
D3.1	Data collection and harmonisation process documentation	3	ZENE	M14	OHB-DS, UNI
D3.2	Report on SPATRA technology development for road transport use case	3	Twist	M20	UNI, ZENE
D3.3	Report on SPATRA technology development for rail transport use case	3	OHB-DS	M20	Twist, ZENE
D4.1	Pilot Plan and Protocol Specification	4	Nelt	M6	UNI, ZENRS
D4.2	Integration and Validation Report	4	ZENE	M22	OHB-DS, UNI
D4.3	Pilot Results and Analysis Report	4	UNI	M24	OHB-DS, ZENE
D5.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	5	OHB-DS	M3	ZENRS
D5.2	SPATRA exploitation plan	5	ZENRS	M24	OHB-DS, UNI

2.3 Deliverable writing

This Section provides guidelines and rules to be followed by all SPATRA deliverable contributors while providing content to the various documents. By using the provided templates and following the guidelines mentioned below, the homogeneity, clarity, and high-level quality of all SPATRA deliverables is ensured despite the multi-contributor nature of the process.

2.3.1 Templates for deliverables, presentations and meetings

Specific templates for documents, presentations and meeting minutes have been created for the SPATRA project and are available on the project internal repository. All the templates include the SPATRA project logo as well as a clear statement regarding the received funding from the European commission, which enables the presented outcome. Additionally, the following disclaimer should be included at the beginning (Deliverable template) of each SPATRA deliverable, clarifying that the SPATRA documents do not necessarily represent the views of the European Union:

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2.4 Quality of communication between the partners-meetings

In order to effectively merge the partners' expertise and knowledge in a distributed project such as SPATRA, it is of highest importance to realise an effective communication among the partners. Project meetings are one of the standard project coordination means to enable that results of the individual partners are internally communicated in the project and brought together to realize the project objectives. Whenever possible the face-to-face meetings will be organised, which are especially important for good communication among the partners in a project such as SPATRA, which draws on groups with different backgrounds, will be of the following types:

- Project general meetings – will be organised yearly at Consortium level;
- Project technical meetings – will be called at WP level depending on the project progress dynamics;
- Small group technical meetings – will be the meetings between smaller number of partners, mostly between two partners. These meetings will be organised at WP/Task levels. Such meetings will be particularly intensified during the integration and evaluation phase.

In support to face-to-face meetings and with the goal to cope with geographical distribution of project partners, OHB-DS as the project coordinator also introduced and enabled using of Microsoft Teams for organising effective web meetings with the possibilities of sharing files. These web meetings, which will complement face-to-face meetings, will be organised:

- at the Consortium level (project progress meetings and WP leaders' meetings), and
- at the WP/Task level.

Depending on the dynamic of the WPs progresses, regular weekly web meetings or meetings on call will be organised during the project lifetime. All meetings planned within the project will be professionally organized and the Actions agreed in the meeting will be documented.

Prior to the meeting

The meeting organiser will prepare a draft agenda in consultation with the coordinator to be sent to all partners of the project prior to the meeting for comment and feedback.

After the meeting

After the meeting, the meeting organiser/ Project manager/ Coordinator will prepare and send each member of the project a draft minutes of the meeting for comment. Once these minutes have been revised and approved, the final version will be distributed to partners and added to the SPATRA document SharePoint.

3 Risks management strategy

The following Section describes the risk management strategy put in place for SPATRA project. OHB DS as the project coordinator, ensures risk management within the project and performs the Risk Management activities.

The Risk Management process is applied at every stage of the project's development. It consists of an iterative process of estimating, evaluating, mitigating and controlling risks in order to ensure that adequate countermeasures are undertaken. Risk Analysis will be continuously undertaken by the project coordinator, supported by the partners teams' members, by means of measuring the effectiveness of the mitigation plan and ad hoc meetings. Risk analysis and the mitigation actions advancement will be addressed in each project progress meeting, organised by the project coordinator, and at the General Assembly (GEAS) meeting.

Since a project risk is understood as an uncertain event or condition that, if it occurs, has a positive or negative effect on a project's objectives, the SPATRA project intends to identify not only threats but also opportunities.

A negative Risk must be managed in order to avoid that they become issues (prevention) or that their initially expected effect becomes actual (protection). Issues must be treated as soon as possible.

The risk management in SPATRA can be broken down in a set of four main tasks (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Methodology of risk management within SPATRA.

3.1 Risk identification

In order to guarantee an effective project risk management, the risk identification will be done:

- ✓ as soon as possible, starting from this bidding phase, with the view to define the budget and the economic evaluation,
- ✓ including all possible sources of risk, taking into account all perspectives (stakeholders) and different scenarios involved in the management of the project.
- ✓ iteratively repeated during the project life cycle. The identification process must be repeated especially upon the approaching of key events or significant changes in the project.
- ✓ clear risk description and with an appropriate level of detail so as to assign an owner who is responsible for their management, timing and so as to identify the most effective response actions.

In order to correctly identify the risk, it must be described in a rational and structured manner, distinguishing the causes from the risk events and from the effects on the project objectives and milestones. This method allows to better understand the nature of identified risk and facilitates the identification of the specific risk response actions.

3.2 Risk assessment

Both qualitative and quantitative risk analysis are performed, in order to assess the Risk Priority Index (RPI). Appropriate mitigation actions and protective measures will be identified for the

residual risk. In this phase risks are evaluated in terms of *impact* on the project objective and *probability* of occurrence.

Impact: An assessment of the impact a risk consequence may have on an overall program. The adopted default three levels classification is shown in Table 2.

Probability: The probability of occurrence is expressed as a percentage. It represents the Consortium’s assessment of the likelihood that a risk may happen. Default identified probabilities are shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Five levels of risk classifications for risk assessment

Impact	Impact Index I_i
Low	1
Medium	2
High	3

Table 3. Five levels of risk probability

Probability	Probability Index I_p
Low (<33%)	1
Medium (from 34% to 65%)	2
High (> 66%)	3

The RPI (Risk Priority Index) is calculated through the formula $RPI = I_p \cdot I_i$ and is reflected in the Risk Matrix (Figure 2). Within this document, the risks with $RPI < 2$ will be referred to as LOW risks (green cells in Fig.2); the risks with $3 \leq RPI < 6$ as MEDIUM risks (white cells in Fig. 2); and finally, the risks with $RPI \geq 6$ as HIGH risks (orange and red cells in Fig.2). The need for risk mitigation is defined by their RPI in the following way: medium and high risks must be managed through specific mitigation actions and low risks must only need to be monitored by the Project Manager (PM).

		3	6	9
3	3	6	9	
2	2	4	6	
1	1	2	3	
		1	2	3

Probability Index $I_p \rightarrow$

Impact Index $I_i \rightarrow$

Figure 2. Risks matrix (self-created).

3.3 Risk treatment action plan

The objective of this phase is the identification and choice of the mitigation actions to be implemented so as to reduce the probability of occurrence and/or the impact of each “key risk”. The resources in charge of carrying out the above actions are identified at the same time. Main output of this phase is the completion of the Risk Matrix. In this matrix all the relevant results of the risk management process described above are reported, and in particular:

- ✓ the identified risks (ID and name).
- ✓ probability of occurrence (as a percentage) pre and post mitigation actions.
- ✓ impact on project objectives (3 levels classification) pre and post mitigation actions.
- ✓ identified mitigation actions (typology of mitigation).
- ✓ actions plan (identification of actions to be carried for the risk mitigation with identification of the action owner, dates and timelines).

All the identified mitigation actions will be included in the project tasks planning (in the same way as the other project execution tasks) and their costs include in the project budget. After the identification of the mitigation actions, the “residual risk” is estimated. The residual risk is defined as the remaining risks after the implementation of the mitigation actions. The risk evaluation phase and the risk treatment phase are repeated, and the new Risk Register compiled.

3.4 Risk monitoring and report

An efficient Risk Management process cannot exclude a careful and constant monitoring activity of the trend and evolution of risks. The objective of this phase is to:

- ✓ update the risk status.

- ✓ verify the execution and effectiveness of the mitigation Actions Plan.
- ✓ identify and evaluate new risks, according to the already described risk management process.

The Project Coordinator, with the support of the Scientific & Technical Manager, will continuously monitor the progress of work and risks of underperformance. For this, bi-weekly online project meetings will be held, where the WP leaders will report on the work progress in their respective WP, especially highlighting arising difficulties which may potentially affect the outcome of each task and WP. The SPATRA Risk Register is stored in an online shared repository and will be updated by the Scientific & Technical Manager on a bi-weekly basis during each of the bi-weekly project meetings. The format of an online-meeting allows both introducing new potential risks into the register and also evaluate the status and, if applicable, mitigation efficacy of the previously added risks. An updated Risk Register will be transmitted regularly during the project to the project coordinator (PC) and any time that an event (external or internal to the project) could potentially impact the objective of the project.

In case PC notices a case or a risk of serious underperformance, PC may notify the Consortium of its observations and require the consortium's management and GA to report at short notice proposing quick remedial actions.

The first SPATRA Risk Register is included already in GA-Part A (List of Critical Risks). In the following Table 4, this list, containing 11 identified risks, is extended in the first iteration with the further identified risks, mainly concerning the technical Work Packages 3 and 4. The workflow of the project will be closely monitored for newly arising risks throughout the entire project lifetime, and risk assessment and mitigation work will be done according to approach described in Figure 1.

Table 4. Critical risks and risk management strategy

Risk number	Description	Work Package No(s)	Probability	Impact	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Loss of personnel	WP1	Low	High	Redistribution of work
2	Work is behind schedule	WP1	Low	High	Redistribution of tasks and/or involvement of further personnel.
3	Important project members leave the project/the company.	WP1	Low	High	Knowledge is not concentrated but spread within the team, good work atmosphere in the project. Due to the flat hierarchies and cross-departmental networking, the loss of specialist staff within partners' teams can be balanced out.
4	Lack of input from relevant stakeholders	WP2	Medium	Medium	Partners are well networked with relevant stakeholders, so that failures can be compensated quickly
5	Copernicus Data Services are not available.	WP3	Low	High	Implementation of routines to quickly react to service downtimes to inform the end users and service providers
6	Implementation of downscaling algorithms required, but lack of development time.	WP3	Medium	Medium	Usage of commercial EO data to enable validation of service.
7	Spatial resolution too low for service purpose.	WP3	Medium	Medium	Integration of downscaling algorithm.
8	Temporal resolution too low for service purpose.	WP3	Medium	Medium	Interpolation based on more frequent data (as local weather stations)
9	Technical difficulties in integrating different modules and technologies used in the project.	WP4, WP3	Medium	High	Conducting thorough testing and validation of the technology in various environmental conditions before deploying it in the field
10	Limited availability of drone technology and restrictions on drone usage in some areas.	WP4, WP1	Low	Medium	This can be mitigated by obtaining the necessary permits and certifications for drone operation in urban areas. SPATRA will do that and will analyse regulation in WP1.

11	Difficulties in achieving accurate image recognition and processing in varying weather and lighting conditions.	WP4, WP3	Medium	High	SPATRA will explore and implement advanced imaging and processing techniques that can adapt to different lighting and weather conditions. Additionally, testing and validation of the technology in various weather conditions and lighting scenarios to ensure its accuracy and reliability
12	Insufficient quality of the project dissemination due to low quality of the project deliverables	All WPs	Low	High	In SPATRA, a procedure of internal pre-review is adopted, where project partners not immediately involved in writing a given Deliverable peer-review the document before submission. This procedure ensures high quality of the SPATRA outcomes which in turn aids in quality dissemination to the community and stakeholders. In addition EUSPA introduced a expert pre-review procedure so that the deliverable documents approved by internal reviewers are sent to expert reviewers to be reviewed and consequently improved (if needed) before final submission.
13	Absence of rail buckling risk service due to data gaps caused by persistent cloud cover or by temporary satellite sensor anomalies	WP4, WP3	High	Medium	In case data gaps due to persistent cloud cover or sensor anomalies prevent successful demonstration of service, demonstration will be shifted to another date when the data are available. In case of data gaps during the application phase, local meteorological data for air temperature will be used to derive the rail temperature according to the published approach (Hong et al., 2021)
14	Permanent failure of Sentinel-2 or Sentinel-3 sensors or communication with satellite	WP4, WP3	Low	High	As both Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 missions consist of two satellites each (platform A and B), the probability of complete EO data failure of these missions is extremely low. In this unlikely event, freely available data from other platforms like Landsat 8,9 (instead of Sentinel-2) and Visible Infrared Imaging

					Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) or Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instead of Sentinel-3 will be used.
15	EGNSS signal low	WP3, WP4	Medium	High	Location trackers enabled with EGNSS interface could have low visibility or can be unavailable at the time of data collection. Dual data interface could be used as a supportive measure to transfer to GPS if EGNSS is not working.
16	Drone AI/ML truck or parking occupancy recognition low	WP3, WP4	Low	High	Algorithm deployed on the drone will be used to detect the object from the camera images and video. The problem can occur with the accuracy of parking occupancy, and with the ability to detect the number of trucks from the vertical camera. Dataset will be collected, and parking mapped, and preprocessing data established in several iterations analyzing and improving the accuracy of the setup and the AI.

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Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the project SPATRA quality assurance plan – introduces the measures and steps that will provide that project quality is met and quality expectations are achieved. This Project Quality Plan demonstrates that quality aspects are taken into account in a variety of processes and activities within the SPATRA project.

Potential risks have been analysed and their potential effects on the project' progress have been estimated. The risks have been subdivided into minor risks that need to be monitored and key risks which will require mitigation. Mitigation strategies have been suggested for each identified risk. The given Risk mitigation table is the first project Risk mitigation table, and will be reviewed during the project lifetime and updated if needed.

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